

Studies in Ferric Selenite Sol : Potentiometric Determination of the Coagulation Process of the Sol at Its Different Stages of Purity

K. L. HANDOO & A. K. BHATTACHARYA

Department of Chemistry, University of Saugar, Saugar

Received 20 July 1971, revised MSS received 22 March 1972

The mechanism of coagulation of positively charged ferric selenite sol has been discussed with the aid of the results obtained by potentiometrically titrating the sol with K_2SO_4 at its different states of purity. When the sol is sufficiently impure, the quantity of the counter ions released during coagulation is super-equivalent to added electrolyte. The pH of the sol increases during coagulation with the stepwise addition of the electrolyte.

Electrometric determination of the process of coagulation has been made by several workers. In spite of their extensive research the fact remains that no definite constitution could be assigned to the sol particles. Thomas and co-workers¹, in their studies of hydrous oxide sols, stated that the dispersed phase of alumina consisted of solated and possibly oxolated aluminium oxychloride complexes of the Werner type. Weiser² suggested that despite the fact that the particles of alumina sol consisted largely of hydrous oxide, they usually contained some chloride that was difficult to be dislodged. Some workers have studied the variation of pH and electrical conductivity of sols during coagulation and the observed increase of pH , with the addition of K_2SO_4 to some positively charged sols such as hydrous ferric oxide³ and chromium tungstate⁴, has been ascribed to the adsorption of H_3O^+ ions by the partially neutralized surface of the sol particle during coagulation with the consequent increase of OH^- ion concentration of the medium. After an investigation of the coagulation of lyophobic sols by means of radioactive tracer atoms, Glazman, Strazhesko, Zhel'vis and Chervyatsova⁵ hold that the coagulation process is connected not only with the surface of the sol particles but with the inner part of their electrical double layer as well, and the process can not be explained merely by visualizing the electrostatic compression of the double layer. In a further study Glazman and co-workers⁶ suggest that in the coagulation three types of antagonisms are recognised—coagulating ions competing for adsorption places on the surface of the particles; additional adsorption on the surface of the dispersed phase, of ions that determine the potential; electrostatic effects of ions in the volume of the solution and in the electrical field of colloidal particles.

In this paper, an attempt has been made to study the mechanism of coagulation of ferric selenite sol by potentiometrically titrating it with K_2SO_4 at its various forms of purity. A previous communication⁷ deals with the studies of coagulation of chromium selenite sol at various stages of dialysis.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ferric selenite sol was best prepared by peptization method adding dropwise 6% sodium selenite solution to a 20% solution of ferric chloride. The sol thus prepared was kept for dialysis and the samples were withdrawn at different stages of dialysis. The composition of the original sol and that of the other samples obtained by subsequent dialysis was determined and the contents reported as Fe_2O_3 , SeO_3^- , and Cl^- in gms/lit. Table I records the results of such analysis.

TABLE I

Composition and stability of ferric selenite sol at different stages of dialysis

Stages of dialysis	Days of dialysis	Amt. in gms/lit of :			Precipitation value of K_2SO_4 (Millimoles/lit)
		Fe_2O_3	SeO_3^-	Cl	
I	2	5.6480	1.9930	3.1600	4.250
II	3	4.8520	1.9030	1.1010	2.490
III	4	4.8015	1.9005	0.4105	0.875
IV	7	4.7000	1.8800	0.0118	0.200

The sols were titrated with K_2SO_4 solution. The procedure involved the stepwise addition of the electrolyte solution to the sol at its different forms of purity and the measurement of the accompanying changes in the concentration of the counter chloride ions by a potentiometric method. For this purpose, a series of electrolyte solutions were prepared in the increasing order of the concentration of K_2SO_4 so that the middle of the series comprised of the precipitation concentration of the sol under study. In a separate set, 10 ml of the sol of a particular purity were placed in each of several pyrex glass boiling tubes. Sol-electrolyte mixing was now done by adding the electrolyte solutions, each of a volume of 10 ml, to the sol so that the total volume remained 20 ml throughout the set. On the other hand, various vessels with side tubes were arranged for the purpose of setting up calomel half cells to determine chloride ion concentration potentiometrically. A small quantity of pure mercury was placed at the bottom of each cell, and the same was then covered with a paste of pure mercurous chloride and a particular sol-electrolyte mixture. The vessel was then completely filled with the sol-electrolyte mixture saturated with calomel. The nozzle of the side tube dipped in the remaining sol-electrolyte mixture placed in a beaker. The other half cell constituted calomel electrode with 0.1N KCl solution. After having left the mixtures for twelve hours to attain equilibrium, the potential was determined after placing a salt bridge, consisting of saturated KCl solution, between the two solutions which minimized the liquid junction potential to a favourable experimental determination. In this way potential of each half cell was observed and a modified form of Nernst equation employed to calculate the activity (a_{Cl}) of the chloride ions. Use was made of the graph of Lewis and Randall⁸ to read the corresponding activity coefficient (f) whereafter the value of molar concentration could be obtained from the expression $[\text{Cl}] = \frac{a_{\text{Cl}}}{f}$. The added electrolyte is expressed in terms of equivalent amount of chloride.

For the *pH* measurements, sol-electrolyte mixtures were prepared in the same way as mentioned above. A Marconi *pH* meter (type TF 717A) using glass and saturated calomel electrodes was used for this purpose.

DISCUSSION

It is observed from Tables 2 and 3 that when the sols are sufficiently contaminated with the stabilizing electrolyte, super-equivalent release of chloride ions takes place on adding K_2SO_4 . Such results were earlier reported by Rabinowitsch and Kargin⁹ and by Yadava¹⁰ who, while studying the coagulation of ferric hydroxide sol, described that the excessive release of the counter ions was due to their presence originally at the surface of the colloid particles in the form of ion pairs. Contrary to this, Weiser¹¹ found that the displaced chloride was always less than the amount of the electrolyte added when expressed in chlorine equivalent. It is interesting to note, however, that in the present case, the same sol which showed super-equivalent release of chloride ions initially behaved differently at its purer form: the displaced chloride in this case was less than the chlorine equivalent of the electrolyte (vide tables 4 and 5). The results thus were now similar to those obtained by Weiser.

TABLE 2

Potentiometric Titration of Ferric Selenite Sol with K_2SO_4

Sol. 1

(Precipitation value : 4.25 millimoles/lit)

MLN/40 K_2SO_4 added to 10 ml. sol. Total Vol. 20 ml.	K_2SO_4 Conc. in terms of millimoles/ lit.	<i>pH</i>	Volt	Cl^- $\times 10^3$	$[Cl^-]$ $\times 10^3$	$[Cl^-]$ displaced $\times 10^3$	$[Cl^-]$ equivalent to $[SO_4]$ added $\times 10^3$
0	0.000	1.40	0.03545	19.95	22.25	0.00	0.00
1	0.625	1.42	0.03338	20.80	23.75	1.50	1.25
2	1.250	1.44	0.03306	21.90	25.00	2.75	2.50
3	1.875	1.45	0.03207	22.75	26.05	3.80	3.75
4	2.500	1.47	0.03034	24.35	27.80	5.55	5.00
5	3.125	1.48	0.02896	25.70	29.83	7.58	6.25
6	3.750	1.50	0.02660	28.19	32.54	10.29	7.50
7	4.375	1.55	0.02578	29.08	34.10	11.85	8.75
8	5.000	1.58	0.02440	30.70	35.61	13.36	10.00
9	5.625	1.59	0.02390	31.25	36.11	13.86	11.25
10	6.250	1.60	0.02380	31.31	36.40	14.15	12.50

It is further seen from tables 2-5, that there is a continuous increase of *pH* of the sol during its coagulation and this trend persists even with the purer sols.

The following picture of the process of coagulation is suggested. Ferric selenite sol, in the initial stages of dialysis, has a relatively large quantity of ferric chloride present in the dispersion medium (vide table 1) and so there will be adsorption of Fe^{+3} ions and also of H^+ ions at some active centres of the lattice and consequently a double layer will be set

up with chloride as counter ions. The constitution of the particle itself without the double layer is so complex that a definite formula cannot be assigned to it. Similarly any attempt to formulate the mode of lattice-fitting of the stabilizing ions will be futile unless some heed is given to a possible inclusion of H_2O and HCl molecules associated with the lattice. However the important thing remains that the adsorbed ion which fits the lattice sufficiently well only gets distributed in two phases and thus serves as potential determining ion. The nature and extent of association of these molecules which may be represented as αH_2O , βHCl will not be explored presently, but it is certain that the magnitude of such association gets lessened with the progress of dialysis.

TABLE 3

Sol. 2

(Precipitation value : 2.490 millimoles/lit)

Ml., N/60 K_2SO_4 added to 10 ml.sol. Total Vol. 20 ml.	K_2SO_4 Conc. in terms of millimoles/ lit.	pH	Volt	αCl^- $\times 10^3$	$[Cl^-]$ $\times 10^3$	$[Cl^-]$ displaced $\times 10^3$	$[Cl^-]$ equivalent to $[SO_4]$ added $\times 10^3$
0	0.000	1.80	0.0700	5.19	5.49	0.00	0.000
1	0.416	1.82	0.0605	7.52	8.04	4.56	0.833
2	0.833	1.83	0.0539	9.73	10.67	5.18	1.666
3	1.249	1.84	0.0500	11.32	12.35	6.86	2.499
4	1.666	1.86	0.0479	12.30	13.56	8.07	3.332
5	2.082	1.87	0.0471	12.68	13.95	8.46	4.165
6	2.499	1.88	0.0467	12.86	14.24	8.75	4.998
7	2.915	1.89	0.0459	13.24	14.67	9.18	5.831
8	3.332	1.89	0.0453	13.66	15.16	9.15	6.664
9	3.748	1.89	0.0447	13.90	15.51	10.01	7.497
10	4.165	1.89	0.0440	14.30	16.00	10.51	8.330

TABLE 4

Sol. 3

(Precipitation value : 0.875 millimoles/lit)

Ml.N/200 K_2SO_4 added to 10 ml.sol. Total Vol. 20 ml.	K_2SO_4 Conc. in terms of millimoles/ lit.	pH	Volt	αCl^- $\times 10^3$	$[Cl^-]$ $\times 10^3$	$[Cl^-]$ displaced $\times 10^3$	$[Cl^-]$ equivalent to $[SO_4]$ added $\times 10^3$
0	0.000	2.18	0.0732	4.58	4.80	0.00	0.00
1	0.125	2.27	0.0728	4.66	5.01	0.21	0.25
2	0.250	2.30	0.0710	5.00	4.37	0.57	0.50
3	0.375	2.33	0.0706	5.08	5.46	0.66	0.75
4	0.500	2.35	0.0700	5.20	5.50	0.70	1.00
5	0.625	2.37	0.0695	5.30	5.61	0.81	1.25
6	0.750	2.38	0.0688	5.43	5.75	0.95	1.50
7	0.875	2.39	0.0679	5.66	6.01	1.21	1.75
8	1.000	2.40	0.0670	5.84	6.15	1.35	2.00
9	1.125	2.40	0.0667	5.93	6.25	1.45	2.25
10	1.250	2.41	0.0665	5.94	6.27	1.47	2.50

TABLE 5

Sol. 4

(Precipitation value : 0.200 millimoles/lit)

ML.,N/1000 K ₂ SO ₄ added to 10 ml.sol. Total Vol. 20 ml.	K ₂ SO ₄ Conc. in terms of millimoles/ lit.	pH	Volt	α Cl ⁻ $\times 10^3$	[Cl ⁻] $\times 10^3$	[Cl ⁻] displaced $\times 10^3$	[Cl ⁻] equivalent to [SO ₄] added $\times 10^3$
0	0.000	3.83	0.1280	0.5418	0.5500	0.000	0.00
1	0.025	4.00	0.1260	0.5869	0.5920	0.042	0.05
2	0.050	4.12	0.1253	0.6037	0.6210	0.071	0.10
3	0.075	4.20	0.1242	0.6292	0.6350	0.085	0.15
4	0.100	4.23	0.1235	0.6269	0.6610	0.111	0.20
5	0.125	4.27	0.1233	0.6500	0.6700	0.120	0.25
6	0.150	4.30	0.1228	0.6610	0.6850	0.135	0.30
7	0.175	4.35	0.1226	0.6690	0.6920	0.142	0.35
8	0.200	4.40	0.1215	0.6995	0.7220	0.172	0.40
9	0.225	4.48	0.1210	0.7125	0.7355	0.185	0.45
10	0.250	4.56	0.1190	0.7705	0.8050	0.255	0.50

When an electrolyte such as K₂SO₄ is added to the sol, chloride ions are displaced to a certain extent from the Stern¹²-Mukherjee¹³ layer and sulphate ions get crowded up near the inner layer. The thickness of the double layer is therefore decreased with the result that the electrical charge on the colloidal particle diminishes by neutralization and a meta-stable condition of the sol is obtained. At this stage, the partially discharged surface of the dispersed phase ceases to hold the linked molecules and develops a tendency to restore the positive charge by holding hydrogen ions by virtue of supplementary adsorption resulting into an orientation of extra chloride ions in the diffuse outer layer to the extent that they become potentiometrically detectable. A large number of hydrogen ions which could be held by supplementary adsorption are available in the dispersion medium as well. It is obvious, therefore, that during this antagonistic stage, the pH of the system should increase (tables 2 to 5). The above viewpoint also explains the super equivalent displacement of the chloride to the quantity of sulphate added. When the sol is, however, kept for prolonged dialysis, chloride ions are considerably washed off from the sol (vide table 1). The composition of the sol particles varies with the state of purity and the magnitude of HCl—lattice association becomes so much lessened that no super-equivalent release of chloride ions is to be expected.

REFERENCES

1. Thomas *et al.*, ("Colloid Chemistry", 1934, Chap. VIII).
2. H. B. Weiser and Gray, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1936, **36**, 2178, 2796.
3. R. S. Rai and S. Ghosh, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1954, **23**, 48, 142.
4. P. C. Jain and S. N. Banerji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 323.
5. Y. M. Glazman, D. N. Strazhesko, E. F. Zhel'vis and L. L. Chervyatsova. *Kolloid Zh.* 1954, **21**, 263.
6. Y. M. Glazman and Co-workers, *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, **56**, 8043.
7. K. L. Handoo, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1971 (in press).
8. Lewis and Randal, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 1132.
9. A. I. Rabinowitsch and Kargin, *Z. Physikal Chem.*, 1928, **133**, 203.
10. B. P. Yadava, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 115, 123.
11. H. B. Weiser, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, **35**, 1.
12. O. Stern, *Z. Electrochem* 1924, **30**, 508.
13. J. N. Mukherjee, *Trans. Faraday, Soc.*, 1921, **16**, 103.